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SOLVING THE PROBLEM OF INTERNAL INSIDE IN FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS

The rapid growth of insider attacks on critical information resources of financial institutions is a pressing concern. The aim of this paper is to develop a set of recommendations for countering insider attacks. This article analyzes the current state of the problem of combating insider attacks in the context of high-level information aggression from the United West. It identifies sources of vulnerabilities and threats to company data that are critical for managing a financial institution and solving priority banking tasks. It also describes the key vulnerabilities and threats that are most likely to occur, and identifies their contribution to informational, economic, and social damage to the financial institution's operations. It also identifies the circle of individuals (company personnel) most frequently exposed to fraudulent actions by attackers, which have a destructive impact on critical information resources and create the conditions for cyber incidents. The causes of critical information resource leaks in financial institutions are identified, their layered structure and detailed characteristics are presented, and the main methods and features of cyberattack planning, preparation, disguise, disinformation, and execution by cybercriminals are outlined. A set of measures aimed at minimizing the toxic impact on the financial institution's critical information resources is proposed as part of organizational measures under the company's information security policy, along with the use of modern technical countermeasures. This article can serve as a source for further research into the development of a methodology for preventing destructive actions by cybercriminals against the financial institution's critical information resources.

Keywords: critical information, resources, threats, leaks, inside information, destructive impact, fraudsters.

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Next-Generation FireWall

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IDS/IPS
[7].

DDoS

[8].

« » (MitM),

[9].

APT-

[10].

APT-

[11].

APT-

OSI, « »

IDS/IPS, IPS),

NGFW (APT [12].

NGFW (Application Control), L3 L7 OSI,

C&C DGA (Domain Generation Algorithm).

C&C [13].

DNS 53 NGFW

FW,

URL, HTTP

NGFW

HTTPS,

NGFW. NGFW. VPN-

(Zero Trust Network Access).

[14].

IPS. NGFW NGFW SSL [15]. NGFW

Sandbox [16]. NGFW, [17].

(Application Security),

[18].

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SAST (Static Application Security Testing) [20], DAST (Dynamic Application Security Testing) [19]

[21].

White Box- (« »)

Static Application Security Testing (SAST) —

SAST

White Box

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Solar appScreener;

(False Positive)

White Box-

Solar
Fuzzy

appScreener,
Logic Engine [23].

White Box-

SAST,

[24].

» (Black Box),
Dynamic Application Security Testing

(DAST).

SAST

White Box

White Box —

Black Box

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DAST

White Box-

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Bug Bounty,
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1. USB- ;
2. , ;
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SIEM-

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